

Vistula University

The Faculty of Computer Engineering, Graphic Design and Architecture

Program of study Computer Science

Chan Duong Nguy

Student number 63408

**Deep Differentiable Logic Gate
Networks Based on Fuzzy Zadeh's
T-norm**

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Dr. Piotr Walsilewski

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Introduction

While training costs receive significant attention in deep learning research, inference costs often have a greater real-world impact, since models are typically trained once but used for inference many times. In production environments, inference efficiency directly affects user experience, operational costs, and energy consumption, making it a critical optimization target. This is especially important for edge devices and real-time applications where computational resources are limited and latency requirements are strict. Existing methods (reduced precision (Choi et al., 2018), (Gupta et al., 2015), binary (Qin et al., 2020), and sparse networks (Hoefler et al., 2021)) have limitations. In the work (Petersen et al., 2022) authors used logic gate networks with a continuous relaxation based on the Menger T-norm (Menger, 1942) to enable gradient-based training. In this paper, we are following this idea by applying a similar technique based on the Zadeh T-norm. The main results presented are adapted from our paper reviewed and presented at the 6th Polish Conference on Artificial Intelligence PP-RAI 2025, 7-9.04.2025 at University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland (Wasilewski & Nguy, 2025).

Logic gate networks are made up of discrete, non-differentiable operations (like “and” and “xor”), which makes training with gradient descent difficult. Traditional gradient-free methods (e.g., evolutionary strategies (Mocanu et al., 2018)) can work for small models but are not practical for larger networks. The authors (Petersen et al., 2022) relax the discrete logic gates into a continuous form so that the network can be trained with the gradient descent. In this paper, instead of the Menger T-norm (Menger, 1942), we use the Zadeh T-norm (Zadeh, 1965) for the continuous relaxation of logic gate operations. However, Zadeh T-norm is not differentiable at $a = b$ therefore we need to assume when $a = b$ we choose a as output. For each neuron, we learn a probability distribution over 16 possible Binary Logic Gates using softmax. After training, each neuron is assigned the most likely (hard) logic gate based on this learned distribution. These networks are naturally sparse (each neuron only takes two inputs) and do not require weights, leading to very fast inference speeds (processing millions of images per second on a single CPU). Using the Zadeh’s T-norm provides a different, potentially more stable and efficient, way to relax the logic operations compared to the Menger’s T-norm.

This research builds directly upon the differentiable logic gate network framework introduced by Petersen and his collaborators (Petersen et al., 2022), which uses the Menger T-norm for continuous relaxation of logic operations. Our main contributions are as follows:

- We extend the existing framework by introducing the Zadeh T-norm as an alternative continuous relaxation method for logic gate networks.
- We adapt the training procedure to accommodate the properties of the Zadeh T-norm, including handling its non-differentiability at $a = b$ by defining an appropriate output choice.
- We conduct a comprehensive empirical comparison between the Zadeh-based networks, the original Menger T-norm networks, and standard fully connected neural networks on benchmark datasets such as MNIST (LeCun et al., 1998).
- We demonstrate that the Zadeh T-norm based networks achieve extremely fast inference speeds on CPU while particularly well-suited for detecting specific singular patterns.

This work draws from multiple areas of prior research: binary neural networks (Qin et al., 2020), evolutionary logic network training (Mocanu et al., 2018), differentiable logic using T-norms (Petersen et al., 2022), and continuous relaxations of discrete functions (Petersen, 2022; Petersen et al., 2021). The Zadeh and Menger T-norms (Menger, 1942; Zadeh, 1965) are foundational tools in fuzzy logic, and this work shows how they can be adapted to modern deep learning frameworks.

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides historical context and traces the evolution of neural networks from early models like the McCulloch-Pitts neuron to modern architectures.
- **Chapter 2** introduces the theory behind classical, three values and fuzzy logic, Logic Gate Networks, and Differentiable Logic Gate Networks.
- **Chapter 3** describes the proposed Zadeh-based model, including its architecture, training process, and implementation details. Presents experimental results and compares the performance of our approach to baseline models.
- **Chapter 4** analyzes, conclusion of our findings and outlines directions for future research.

Chapter 1

Elements of Neural Network

1.1 Artificial Neural Networks

The seminal paper "A Logical Calculus of the Ideas Immanent in Nervous Activity," published in 1943 by Warren S. McCulloch, a neurophysiologist, and Walter Pitts, a mathematician, laid the theoretical groundwork for artificial neural networks (McCulloch & Pitts, 1943). The research aimed to develop a mathematical model of the nervous system, showing that it can be seen as binary logical units. The authors proposed a simplified computational model for a biological neuron. Their goal was to show that brain activities can be described symbolically with logic. The neuron's output would activate if more than a specific number of its inputs were active, effectively performing logical computations based on propositional logic.

The authors showed that it is possible to simulate a simple neuron with basic logic gates such as AND (\wedge), OR (\vee), and NOT (\neg). In order to represent the relationships and the activities between neurons as propositional logic, the authors had to make several assumptions (McCulloch & Pitts, 1943).

- "All-or-none" nature of neuron activity
- The requirement of a fixed number of simultaneously excited synapses within a brief period (latent addition) to trigger a neuron
- The assumption that synaptic delay was the only significant delay in the system
- The principle of absolute inhibition, where an active inhibitory synapse completely prevents a neuron's excitation

Formally, a neuron can be described as:

$$N_i(z_1) = S \left\{ \bigwedge_{m=1}^q \neg N_{jm}(z_1) \cdot \bigvee_{a \in k_i} \bigwedge_{s \in a} N_{is}(z_1) \right\},$$

where $N_i(z_1)$ is the output of neuron i at time z_1 , S is the function that calculates the neuron's threshold (fire or not), N_{jm} is an inhibitory synapse, \neg is logical NOT (inhibition), N_{is} is an excitatory synapse, and \wedge, \vee are logical conjunction and disjunction respectively.

In natural language terms, the equation can be understood as,

$$N_i(z_1) = S\{\text{no inhibition} \wedge \text{sufficient excitation}\}$$

Neuron N_i fires at time z_1 if none of the inhibitory neurons are firing, and at least one subset of its excitatory inputs is firing.

The research goal was to uncover the foundational principles of how we think and to develop practical applications. They aimed for what they termed an “experimental epistemology” to connect the mind and brain. Yet, the paper marked a pivotal moment in the history of computing and artificial intelligence. It introduced the concept of artificial neurons and provided a mathematical representation of neurons. The simplicity and elegance of this model, where a neuron’s firing is determined by a threshold on the weighted sum of its inputs, established a standard of reference that continues to be influential in the field of neural networks. This laid the theoretical foundation for all later developments in neural computation, establishing a connection between brain activity and symbolic logic. While the McCulloch-Pitts model provided a powerful abstraction for understanding neural activity through logic, it lacked a crucial capability: the ability to learn from experience. All connections and behaviors in their model had to be explicitly defined, limiting its practical application. To overcome this limitation, subsequent research introduced mechanisms that allowed artificial neurons to adjust their behavior based on data. This led to the development of the perceptron—a significant evolution of the original model that incorporated learning through weight updates, marking the first step toward adaptive and trainable neural networks.

1.2 Perceptron and Non-linear Separability

Building upon the foundational symbolic neuron model introduced by McCulloch and Pitts (McCulloch & Pitts, 1943), Frank Rosenblatt (Rosenblatt, 1958) introduced Perceptron as a the mathematical model of the neuron. In 1969, Minsky and Papert provided a comprehensive mathematical analysis of a simplified version of Rosenblatt’s model (Rosenblatt, 1958) in their influential work “Perceptrons” (Minsky & Papert, 1969).

1.2.1 Perceptron

In contrast to the symbolic model of McCulloch and Pitts, Rosenblatt’s perceptron introduced a data-driven learning mechanism, enabling the model to adjust its internal parameters specifically the input weights via a simple learning rule. A typical perceptron model includes an input layer and a single output neuron, and is commonly classified as a shallow neural network. This formulation represented a substantial step toward the development of adaptive neural networks capable of learning from data.

A single-layer perceptron with n input features (x) and one output (\hat{y}) can be expressed

Figure 1.1: Perceptron with n number of inputs, threshold activation, and one output

Source: Dr. Piotr Wasilewski's Lecture In Artificial Intelligence at Vistula University.

mathematically as a linear transformation between x and w :

$$\hat{y} = \theta(xw + b), \quad (1.1)$$

where $x \in \mathbf{R}^{1 \times n}$ denotes the input vector, $w \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times 1}$ the learnable weight vector, $b \in \mathbf{R}$ the bias term, and θ is a threshold activation function defined as:

$$\theta(o) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } o \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

An equivalent, more concise representation assumes that the input vector x is augmented with a leading value of 1, allowing the bias to be absorbed into the weight vector:

$$\hat{y} = \theta(xw),$$

see figure 1.1 Weight updates in the perceptron model were guided by a variation of Hebbian learning (Hebb, 1949, 2002; Shaw, 1986) known as the Delta Rule:

$$\Delta w_i = \eta \delta x_i = \eta (y - \hat{y}) x_i, \quad (1.3)$$

where η denotes the learning rate, it is often in the range of $(0, 1]$. A central focus of Minsky and Papert's critique lies in their formal proofs outlining the limitations of the perceptron, notably its inability to model certain functions such as the exclusive OR (XOR), which are not linearly separable.

1.2.2 Non-linear Separability

Logical functions such as XOR and its complement NXOR (logical equivalence) expose a fundamental limitation of single-layer perceptrons: the inability to handle problems requiring non-

linear decision boundaries. The geometric interpretation of this limitation can be visualized by projecting the output of logical gates onto two-dimensional input planes, as illustrated in Figure 1.2. This analysis reveals a structural constraint on the representational capacity of the percep-

Figure 1.2: Linear separability in logical gates: AND, OR (linearly separable) vs. XOR (not linearly separable).

Source: Own elaboration.

tron, one that cannot be overcome by merely increasing the number of training examples or stacking more perceptrons without hidden layers (Minsky & Papert, 1969).

Interestingly, McCulloch and Pitts neuron model (McCulloch & Pitts, 1943) simulate the brain activities on the basis of with logical connectives AND, OR, NOT and show that ANN can be described symbolically. Therefore, by nature, their model can solve the non-linear separability of XOR which interm solve the NXOR problem.

Although Minsky and Papert briefly acknowledged the theoretical potential of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) or Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) to overcome such limitations, they also highlighted the absence of a feasible training algorithm for adjusting weights in the hidden layers at the time. DNNs, which consist of multiple layers of neurons interconnected through non-linear activation functions, eventually provided a solution to the representational limitations of single-layer models and laid the foundation for modern deep learning.

Let f_i denote a perceptron like transformation with a non-linear activation function at layer i . A feedforward MLP with n layers can then be described as a nested composition of such functions:

$$\hat{y} = f_n \circ f_{n-1} \circ \dots \circ f_1. \quad (1.4)$$

Because of this, ANNs did not gain widespread practical utility until the development of the backpropagation algorithm (Rumelhart et al., 1986), which provided an efficient method for

computing gradients through multiple layers, enabling end-to-end training of deep networks.

1.3 Gradient Based Learning

As Neural Networks grow larger, the need for more effective training methods increases. This was addressed with the introduction of the backpropagation algorithm in the 1986 paper (Rumelhart et al., 1986). This algorithm, also known as the Generalized Delta Rule or simply backpropagation, provided a robust method for training multi-layer neural networks.

The core principle of backpropagation is to iteratively adjust the weights of neural networks to minimize the difference between the network output and the expected output. Training consists of two main phases: a forward pass and a backward pass. During the forward pass of an MLP, the network accepts an input vector and produces an output vector after a series of activation functions and matrix multiplications. In the backward pass, the error between the network's output and the desired output is calculated. This error signal is then propagated back through the network, layer by layer, using calculus techniques such as partial derivatives and the chain rule.

1.3.1 Generalized Delta Rule

The Generalized Delta Rule is based on adjusting the weights according to the error signal. For a weight that connects input i to output j , and a sample s in our dataset, the change in weight ($\Delta_s w_{ji}$) is proportional to the learning rate η , the error at the output unit j (δ_{sj}), and the input unit i (x_{si}). To be more precise, suppose we have a shallow network (no hidden layer), no threshold activation function, and we use squared differences for our loss function,

$$L_s = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j (y_{sj} - \hat{y}_{sj})^2 \quad (1.5)$$

where y_{sj} and \hat{y}_{sj} are the ground truth and prediction at sj , respectively.

Let us consider two differentiable functions f and g . The chain rule allows us to express the derivative of the composition $\hat{y} = g(f(x))$ as:

$$\frac{d\hat{y}}{dx} = \frac{dg}{df} \frac{df}{dx}$$

Further more the partial derivative of a multivariable function is just the derivative with respect to one variable at a time, treating all the other variables as constants. Let us consider a function

$f = x_1w_1 + x_2w_2 + w_3$ the partial derivative with respect to w_2 :

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial f}{\partial w_2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial w_2}(x_1w_1 + x_2w_2 + w_3) \\ \frac{\partial f}{\partial w_2} &= 0 \cdot 0 + x_2 \cdot 1 + 0 \\ \frac{\partial f}{\partial w_2} &= x_2\end{aligned}$$

Here, we treat x_1 , w_1 , w_2 , w_3 as constants and the only term that involves w_2 is x_2w_2 .

Then, based on the chain rule, and partial derivative, we have:

$$\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial w_{ji}} = \frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \hat{y}_{sj}} \frac{\partial \hat{y}_{sj}}{\partial w_{ji}} \quad (1.6)$$

One can understand this equation as the rate of change of the loss function for sample s with respect to a weight (w_{ji}) that connect output j to input i is proportional to how much the loss function changes when the output of the model changes ($\partial L_s / \partial \hat{y}_{sj}$), and how much the model output changes when the model weights change ($\partial \hat{y}_{sj} / \partial w_{ji}$).

From equation (1.5), we have:

$$\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \hat{y}_{sj}} = -(y_{sj} - \hat{y}_{sj}) = -\delta_{sj}$$

To simplify the prove we will assume that our network have no activation function, therefore \hat{y}_{sj} can be calculate with:

$$\hat{y}_{sj} = \sum_i w_{ji}x_{si},$$

thus,

$$\frac{\partial \hat{y}_{sj}}{\partial w_{ji}} = x_{si}$$

From equation (1.6), we then have:

$$\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial w_{ji}} = -\delta_{sj}x_{si}$$

This tells us the direction in which the loss function *increase* when we change the weight w_{ji} by a small amount. The direction we are interested in is to *decrease* the loss. Therefore, the rate of change for sample s of a weight (w_{ji}) in a network without a hidden layer is simply:

$$\Delta_s w_{ji} = \eta \delta_{sj} x_{si} = \eta (y_{sj} - \hat{y}_{sj}) x_{si}$$

This equation brings us back to the Delta Rule (equation 1.3) in the last section. The Generalized

Delta Rule, or backpropagation, tells us that we can apply the same logic for hidden layers.

Suppose we have an MLP with n hidden layers. We rewrite equation 1.4 as

$$\hat{y} = f_n \circ f_{n-1} \circ \cdots \circ f_1$$

where f_k are layers in the network. For simplification, let each f_k be a perceptron with a linear activation, i.e., no threshold activation function. Suppose we want to find the rate of change of the loss function with respect to the weights at layer m that connect input i to output j , and let the input to f_m be x , the Generalized Delta Rule gives us:

$$\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial w_{mij}} = \frac{\partial L_s}{\partial f_n} \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial f_{n-1}} \cdots \frac{\partial f_{m+1}}{\partial f_m} \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial w_{mij}}$$

We know that

$$x_{si} = \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial w_{mij}},$$

and the rest form

$$-\delta_{mj} = \frac{\partial L_s}{\partial f_n} \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial f_{n-1}} \cdots \frac{\partial f_{m+1}}{\partial f_m}.$$

Recall that we are interested in the decrease direction of gradient w.r.t w_{mji} therefore we need to multiply it by minus one to change the direction of the gradient. Once again this brings us back to the Delta Rule (equation 1.3):

$$\Delta_s w_{mji} = \eta \delta_{sj} x_i$$

1.3.2 Semi-linear activation functions

For the algorithm to work, all the calculations within the model need to be differentiable. The original DNNs were not compatible with backpropagation because the threshold function (equation 1.2) is not continuous. We can prove this by checking the left and right limits of the function at 0:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^-} \theta(x) &= 0, & \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \theta(x) &= 1 \\ \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^-} \theta(x) &\neq \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \theta(x) \Rightarrow \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \theta(x) \text{ does not exist,} \end{aligned}$$

therefore

$$\theta(x) \text{ is discontinuous at } x = 0$$

Thus, replacing the step function with a semi-linear, non-decreasing, continuous function is necessary for backpropagation to work. Commonly used functions include: Sigmoid ($\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$), Hyperbolic Tangent ($\tanh(x)$), and ReLU ($\max(0, x)$).

This paper is widely regarded as a major milestone in the field, providing a practical and effective method for training complex, multi-layered neural networks.

Figure 1.3: Elman's Recurrent Neural Networks (left), unfolded Elman's Recurrent Neural Networks (right)

Source: By fdeloche, CC BY-SA 4.0, Wikipedia.

1.4 Recurrent Neural Networks

Processing data where the order of data is important, such as time series data or natural language, requires the network to learn the temporal relations between past events and current events. This poses a challenge for traditional Neural Networks. To address this problem, the cognitive scientist Jeffrey L. Elman introduced Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) (Elman, 1990, 1991) by introducing recurrent connections from the input to neural networks. This type of feedback enables DNNs to learn the temporal patterns between past events and current events. The Elman network architecture comprises four main layers: an input layer, a hidden layer, a context layer, and an output layer see figure 1.3. The context layer is the key feature that helps RNNs to learn the relation between past and current events by storing the past output in the context layer. This enables the network to incorporate the past input with the current input by using learnable weights to allow the network to learn the influence of past input on current inputs.

For this to be possible, Elman RNNs' layers consist of two shallow neural networks with linear activation and the same output size. The network f_i takes input x_t where t is discrete time,

$$f_i(x_t) = x_t w_i + b_i.$$

The other network f_h calculates how to incorporate data from hidden state $t - 1$ to the current state,

$$f_h(h_{t-1}) = h_{t-1} w_h + b_h.$$

The output is the element-wise addition with Hyperbolic Tangent activation,

$$h_t = \tanh(f_i(x_t) + f_h(h_{t-1})),$$

h_t is then used for the next calculation (x_{t+1}).

Through a series of experiments, Elman demonstrated the network's ability to learn intricate

temporal structures in sequences, including the sequential order of letters in words, the concept of a "word" emerging from a continuous stream of letters, and even complex lexical classes based on word order in sentences. (Elman, 1990, 1991)

The author's work has greatly influenced research in temporal learning in Artificial Intelligence by demonstrating the effectiveness of recurrent networks trained with backpropagation for processing sequential data. Furthermore, his approach was groundbreaking in the cognitive science field because it represented a departure from the prevailing focus on pre-defined linguistic units. It explored the possibility that such units could emerge through learning over the raw input stream. The concept of recurrent connection laid the foundation for much of the subsequent research in RNNs, including the development of more sophisticated architectures like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997) networks, Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) (Dey and Salem, 2017), and State Space Models (SSMs) (Dao & Gu, 2024). These architectures were designed to address the limitations of RNNs in learning very long-range dependencies and their unparallelizable nature due to their sequential structure.

1.5 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are specialized architectures of multilayer Neural Networks. CNNs are efficient for processing unstructured data such as images. To achieve this, CNNs leverage three key ideas: local receptive fields, shared weights (through convolutional kernels), and spatial or temporal subsampling (pooling). By focusing only on local features and then applying the same kernels across all the patches of data, this significantly reduces the parameter count. These designs allow CNNs to learn hierarchical representations of features directly from raw pixel data. Lower layers (nearer to the inputs) learn simple features like edges and corners, while higher layers (nearer to the outputs) combine these to recognize more complex patterns and objects.

A landmark model in the development of CNNs was LeNet-5, created by Yann LeCun and his colleagues in the early 1990s, primarily for the task of handwritten digit recognition. LeNet-5's (Lecun et al., 1998) architecture typically consists of several layers, including convolutional layers that convolve the input image with learnable kernels to produce feature maps, subsampling (pooling) layers that reduce the spatial size of these feature maps, fully connected layers that perform high-level reasoning on the extracted features, and an output layer that produces the final classification see figure 1.4. The input to the LeNet-5 model was generally a 32x32 pixel grayscale image (LeCun et al., 1998). Importantly, CNNs like LeNet are trained using the backpropagation algorithm, allowing the network to learn the optimal weights for its kernels and connections through gradient descent on a loss function that measures the error in its predictions.

Let the input tensor be $X \in \mathbf{R}^{C_{in} \times H_{in} \times W_{in}}$, the output tensor be $Y \in \mathbf{R}^{C_{out} \times H_{out} \times W_{out}}$, and the kernel weights be $K \in \mathbf{R}^{C_{out} \times C_{in} \times K_H \times K_W}$. Then, the convolution operation is defined as:

Figure 1.4: Typical Convolutional Neural Networks with three convolution layers

Source: By Aphex34, CC BY-SA 4.0, Wikipedia.

$$Y_{c_{out},h,w} = \sum_{c_{in}=0}^{C_{in}-1} \sum_{i=0}^{K_H-1} \sum_{j=0}^{K_W-1} X_{c_{in},h+i,w+j} \cdot K_{c_{out},c_{in},i,j} + b_{c_{out}}$$

The kernel slides across the input image, and at each position, an element-wise multiplication is performed between the kernel and the corresponding sub-region of the input image. The results of this multiplication are then summed to produce a single output value in the feature map.

The introduction of CNNs provided an important tool for computer vision. The model architecture gives us a parameter-efficient way to process data, as well as robustness. This shift towards learned features has been a major trend in the evolution of AI. Furthermore, LeNet-5 exhibited strong robustness to distortions and simple geometric transformations. Since the kernels are reused across sub-regions of the input image, when an input image is shifted, the feature maps are shifted without any significant changes in the original feature map. Thus, it is highly effective in real-world scenarios where image quality and object positioning can vary.

A key difference between ANNs and CNNs is that Artificial Neural Networks take weighted sums across all the inputs and assume that features are not ordered in any particular way. This makes them more suitable for structured data. For example, this is good for tabular data, where the features *age*, *income*, and *gender* or *gender*, *age*, and *income* are treated the same in ANNs. In contrast, CNNs rely on local data being ordered in a particular way, either temporally or spatially. If the data is like an image and we permute all the pixels, CNNs will have a hard time to learn the underlying pattern, but not ANNs. This is due to CNNs being unable to find relationships between distant pixels, unlike ANNs. In another word, we can say CNNs have narrower perceptive fields than traditional Neural Networks.

Despite this downside, this architecture has been widely adopted and further developed. Notable advancements include:

- **AlexNet** (Krizhevsky et al., 2012): By using CUDA (NVIDIA et al., 2020), the authors scaled up the number of CNN's parameters and tested the limits of the architecture.

- **ResNet** (He et al., 2016): Deeper models such as AlexNet suffer from vanishing gradients. By adding skip connections, ResNet reduces the problem of error attenuation.
- **Diffusion Models** (Ramesh et al., 2021): CNNs remain the backbone of many image generation models.

1.6 Long Short-Term Memory

Built on the work of Jeffrey L. Elman on Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) (Elman, 1990, 1991). Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997) was introduced in 1997 to tackle the persistent problem of gradient vanishing in RNNs when the sequence length becomes too large.

The core of the LSTM architecture is the memory cell, a specialized unit that can maintain its state over time, acting as a repository for information. The flow of information into, out of, and within this memory cell is controlled by three multiplicative gate units.

Compared to RNNs and CNNs, LSTMs are a much more complex architecture. Each LSTM compute unit consists of four RNNs with the mixed use of Sigmoid (σ) and Hyperbolic Tangent (\tanh) activation functions.

Each gate in the LSTM is implemented using two small feedforward networks, which operates similarly to an RNN unit. These gates allow for selective access to the constant error flow within the memory cell, which is key to LSTM's ability to learn long-term dependencies see figure 1.5.

- The input gate (i) regulates the flow of new information into the memory cell, shielding it from irrelevant inputs.
- The output gate (o) controls how much of the memory content influences the output of the LSTM unit and the rest of the network.
- The cell gate (g) controls how much new information to incorporate into the cell memory.
- The forget gate (f) enables the memory cell to selectively forget parts of its previous state, allowing adaptability and preventing stale memory accumulation.

These can be formally expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_t &= \sigma(w_{ii}x_t + b_{ii} + w_{hi}h_{t-1} + b_{hi}) \\
 f_t &= \sigma(w_{if}x_t + b_{if} + w_{hf}h_{t-1} + b_{hf}) \\
 g_t &= \tanh(w_{ig}x_t + b_{ig} + w_{hg}h_{t-1} + b_{hg}) \\
 o_t &= \sigma(w_{io}x_t + b_{io} + w_{ho}h_{t-1} + b_{ho})
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1.5: A cell in a Long Short-Term Memory network

Source: By Guillaume Chevalier, CC BY-SA 4.0, Wikipedia.

The output (h_t) and the cell memory (c_t) can be computed with element-wise multiplication (Hadamard product).

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot g_t$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(c_t)$$

The introduction of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks in 1997 by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber represented a significant breakthrough in the field of recurrent neural networks. LSTM effectively addressed the long-standing vanishing gradient problem that had limited the ability of traditional RNNs to learn dependencies over long sequences. As a result, LSTM outperformed other recurrent network algorithms of the time, including Elman's RNNs.

The impact of LSTM has been profound and far-reaching, leading to its widespread adoption in a vast array of sequence modeling tasks across various domains. It has become a cornerstone of modern deep learning, particularly in applications involving sequential data such as speech recognition, natural language processing (including machine translation, language modeling, and text generation), time series analysis, and many others.

Due to the sequential nature of recurrent-type networks, i.e., in order to calculate the output at time t , the computer needs to wait for the output at time $t - 1$ to finish. This makes these ar-

Table 1.1: Example of a Token Embedding look up table with size $\mathbf{R}^{5 \times 3}$

<i>vocab</i>	<i>pos</i>	0	1	2
cat	0	2	0.1	1.3
kitten	1	0.9	0.3	2
dog	2	2.2	1.5	0.2
eats	3	0.3	0.4	0.1
fish	4	0.7	1.8	0.3

Source: Own elaboration.

chitectures impossible to scale and parallelize efficiently on clusters of GPUs. Thus, the market is shifting towards more parallelizable architectures such as the State-Space Model (SSM) (Dao & Gu, 2024) and the Transformer (Vaswani et al., 2017).

1.7 Attention

In 2017, a team of researchers at Google introduced a groundbreaking neural network architecture called the Transformer in their seminal paper, "Attention Is All You Need" (Vaswani et al., 2017). This architecture represented a significant departure from the dominant sequence transduction models that relied on complex recurrent (i.e. LSTM) or convolutional neural networks. The core innovation of the Transformer was its exclusive reliance on attention mechanisms to model dependencies between input and output sequences, entirely dispensing with recurrence and convolutions. The hypothesis behind this design was that attention alone could be sufficient for tasks like language translation, challenging the prevailing wisdom that recurrence was necessary for sequence modeling.

1.7.1 Token Embedding

Before explaining the Attention mechanism, we need to introduce some notions about token embedding. It is not possible for us to work directly with text. Therefore, before any calculations, we need to treat text as a sequence of unique symbols called tokens. The collection of tokens is called a vocabulary (*vocab*), and there are a finite number of them derived from the training dataset. Each token is assigned a unique index called *pos*. This conversion is also known as tokenization.

Modeling sequences is hard without the help of recurrence or convolution, as raw data can be difficult for the network to interpret (Vaswani et al., 2017). Positional encoding consists of three steps. First is token embedding. Each token by itself does not carry any meaning, so we assign each token a randomly initialized vector of length d_{model} . During backpropagation, the network will learn how to move these tokens in the embedding space so that they are most convenient for the model (see Table 1.1).

Then a sentence *kitten kitten eats fish* can be embedded as:

$$token_embedding(s) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9 & 0.3 & 2 \\ 0.9 & 0.3 & 2 \\ 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.1 \\ 0.7 & 1.8 & 0.3 \end{bmatrix}$$

The second step is calculating positional encoding. The authors suggest using fixed sinus and cosinus functions of different frequencies:

$$positional_encoding = \begin{cases} 2i & : \sin(pos/10000^{2i/d_{model}}) \\ 2i + 1 & : \cos(pos/10000^{2i/d_{model}}) \end{cases}$$

Here, pos is the unique value assigned to each token, and i is the index of the scalar in the embedding vector. Lastly, we add the positional encoding to the token embedding: ($x = token_embedding(s) + positional_encoding$). Visually, it can look like this:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9 & 0.3 & 2 \\ 0.9 & 0.3 & 2 \\ 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.1 \\ 0.7 & 1.8 & 0.3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \sin(1/10000^{0/3}) & \cos(1/10000^{0/3}) & \sin(1/10000^{2/3}) \\ \sin(1/10000^{0/3}) & \cos(1/10000^{0/3}) & \sin(1/10000^{2/3}) \\ \sin(3/10000^{0/3}) & \cos(3/10000^{0/3}) & \sin(3/10000^{2/3}) \\ \sin(4/10000^{0/3}) & \cos(4/10000^{0/3}) & \sin(4/10000^{2/3}) \end{bmatrix}$$

The embedding function takes an input $s \in \mathbf{R}^n$ where n is the sequence length, and returns $x \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times d_{model}}$, where d_{model} is the embedding dimension.

1.7.2 Attention Is All You Need

Keeping with this theme, we now explain the Attention mechanism in terms of a system of shallow neural networks. Attention consists of three single-layer neural networks:

- Query (Q): What we're currently "asking" the model to find relevant information for.
- Key (K): Descriptions of all the other tokens in the sequence.
- Value (V): Actual information we'll use once we figure out what's relevant.

Formally, these can be written as:

$$Q = xw_q + b_q$$

$$K = xw_k + b_k$$

$$V = xw_v + b_v$$

Here, $x \in \mathbf{R}^{n, d_{model}}$ is the input, $w_q, w_k, w_v \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times d_{model}}$ are the weights, and $b_q, b_k, b_v \in \mathbf{R}^{d_{model}}$ are the biases. Since Q , K , and V do not use semilinear activation functions, they are also called linear projections. The attention mechanism is a series of linear transformations followed by a softmax:

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V$$

The introduction of the Transformer architecture in “Attention Is All You Need” has had a profound and revolutionary impact on the field of artificial intelligence, particularly in natural language processing. It has become the foundational architecture for most modern Large Language Models (LLMs) and is widely considered a key contributor to the current AI boom. Nowadays, Attention has expanded into many areas of the field such as:

- Computer vision (Han et al., 2023).
- Image synthesis (Ramesh et al., 2021).
- Audio synthesis (Tan et al., 2024), and more.

In fact, when most people refer to recent advancements in AI today, they are often referring to attention-based LLMs.

Chapter 2

Logic Gates and Differentiable Logic Gate Networks

2.1 Logic

The very term "logic" traces its origins to the Greek word "logos," a term rich in meaning, encompassing concepts such as word, thought, idea, argument, account, reason, or principle. This in term show that logic has a very long history, in essence, logic is a study of reasoning. Logic servers as a guide to reduce ambiguity and provide standards for describing facts. The primary objective of logic is to furnish us with the tools necessary to evaluate arguments effectively, allowing us to discern between reasoning that is sound and reasoning that is incorrect.

Two values logic or Binary Logic is a powerful mathematical way to prepresent logic. Where propositions are inputs and logical connectives are functions over these terms. As its name suggest Binary Logic operate on the set of $\mathbf{B} = \{0, 1\}$ where these propositions take on zero (*False*) or one (*True*) values and the logical connectives produce results also in this set. Formally, we can understand logical connectives as functions that map two Boolean values to one Boolean value:

$$f : \mathbf{B}^2 \rightarrow \mathbf{B}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{B} = \{0, 1\},$$

For instance, the AND (\wedge) gate is defined as

$$\wedge : \mathbf{B}^2 \rightarrow \mathbf{B}, \quad x \wedge y = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = y = 1, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since there are four possible inputs for every binary operation this results in there are totally of 16 possible way to map two binary values into one binary value see table 2.1

Classical logic has a weakness where it can not describe unkown state thus there is a need to modify the binary logical function to accept this values. Alone side *True* and *False* three valued logic introduce *Unknown* state to it therefore the set of which three values connectives operate on is $\mathbf{B} = \{0, 0.5, 1\}$ for *False*, *Unknown*, *True* respectively. This addition allows for a more nuanced representation of propositions whose truth value cannot be definitively determined as

Table 2.1: List of 16 possible Binary operations with arity.

ID	00	01	10	11	Operator	Arity
0	0	0	0	0	0	Constant
1	0	0	0	1	$a \wedge b$	Binary
2	0	0	1	0	$\neg(a \Rightarrow b)$	Binary
3	0	0	1	1	a	Unary
4	0	1	0	0	$\neg(a \Leftarrow b)$	Binary
5	0	1	0	1	b	Unary
6	0	1	1	0	$\neg(a \Leftrightarrow b)$	Binary
7	0	1	1	1	$a \vee b$	Binary
8	1	0	0	0	$\neg(a \vee b)$	Binary
9	1	0	0	1	$a \Leftrightarrow b$	Binary
10	1	0	1	0	$\neg b$	Unary
11	1	0	1	1	$a \Leftarrow b$	Binary
12	1	1	0	0	$\neg a$	Unary
13	1	1	0	1	$a \Rightarrow b$	Binary
14	1	1	1	0	$\neg(a \wedge b)$	Binary
15	1	1	1	1	1	Constant

Source: Own elaboration.

either true or false. To calculate this we can use:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a \wedge b &= \min\{a, b\} \\
 a \vee b &= \max\{a, b\} \\
 \neg a &= 1 - a
 \end{aligned}$$

However, there are two different rules for implication Kleene (\Rightarrow_K) and Łukasiewicz (\Rightarrow_L) logics:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a \Rightarrow_K b &= \max\{1 - a, b\} \\
 a \Rightarrow_L b &= \begin{cases} a = b = 0.5 : 1 \\ \text{otherwise} : \max\{1 - a, b\} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

consequently this lead to two cases of $\neg(a \Rightarrow b)$, $a \Leftarrow b$, $\neg(a \Leftarrow b)$.

As we can see it is not possible to adding more and more values to the logic thus there is a need for infinitely many values logic. In 1995 Lotfi Zadeh introduce the theoretical foundation of fuzzy logic is rooted in fuzzy set theory (Zadeh, 1965). Fuzzy logic represents a significant departure from the binary and three values logics by embracing the concept of partial truth. In this system, the truth value of a variable or proposition is not limited to *True* or *False* or *Unknown* but can be any real number within the continuous interval $[0, 1]$. This allows for a much more nuanced representation of truth, acknowledging that many real-world phenomena exist on a spectrum rather than as absolutes. In the paper (Zadeh, 1965), AND (\wedge) and OR (\vee)

Table 2.2: Three famous Fuzzy logic rules in computer science

Rules	Calculation
$T - norm_M$ (Menger, 1942)	ab
$T - norm_Z$ (Zadeh, 1965)	$max\{a, b\}$
$T - norm_L$	$max\{0, a + b - 1\}$

Source: Own elaboration.

connective can be formally written as

$$a \wedge b = T - norm(a, b) = ab$$

$$a \vee b = Co - norm(a, b) = a + b - ab.$$

As there are many rules for fuzzy logic we will shorten fuzzy logic based on Zadeh as $T - norm_Z$ as all 16 connectives can be dedrived from conjunction. Here we provide fuzzy logic rules that commonly teach in University see table 2.2

Fuzzy logic is superset binary logic, thus in the edge cases when the value of the propositions have zero or one these two fuzzy logic regarless of what rules it is based on fuzzy logic degenerates into binary logic.

2.2 Logic Gate Networks

This section and the next explore two interconnected concepts: Logic Gate Networks (LGNs), which utilize traditional binary logic operations, and Differentiable Logic Gate Networks (DLNs), which enable gradient-based learning by relaxing the Binary Logic Gates. Together, these approaches offering both learning capabilities through gradient descent and minimal reduction in model performance. Binary Logic Gates, which operate on binary inputs, are fundamental components in digital circuits. Binary Logic Gates are not always have the same speed: for example trivial gates 0, 3, 5 and 15 are significantly faster than more complex gates such as 6 and 9.

Follow equation 1.1, each neuron computes a weighted sum over its input vector followed by a semilinear activation.

$$\sigma(xw + b),$$

where $x \in \mathbf{R}^n$ represents inputs, $w \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times m}$ represents weights, $b \in \mathbf{R}^m$ is bias, and σ is the activation function this can be Sigmoid, Tanh, ReLU, etc. During training, the weights w are optimized via backpropagation.

In contrast, a Logic Gate Network (LGN) utilizes a different paradigm for processing data, wherein each neuron implements a logic gate operation. Instead of connecting to all inputs, each neuron processes only two binary inputs. Similar to an NN, LGN consists of one or more layers, a layer is an array of Binary Logic Gates. For a binary vector input $x \in \mathbf{B}^n$, pairs of inputs (a, b) are selected from x and used as inputs for logic gates, with their outputs propagating to the next

layer.

An important characteristic of LGNs is their computational efficiency, as they exclusively utilize bit-wise logic operations. This offers both advantages and disadvantages. Binary operations provide much higher computational efficiency than the floating-point operations commonly found in Neural Networks. However, this comes with the limitation that outputs of the model are binary. While single binary outputs for prediction classes are possible (i.e. k outputs or k classes), this approach limits the network’s expressiveness. To address this limitation, multiple neurons’ outputs per class are aggregated through summation. Each neuron effectively captures different evidence for a class, enabling more nuanced predictions. This design allows for probability predictions through a softmax function, converting raw scores (logits) to probabilities. Another disadvantage of bit-wise logic operations is that they are not continuous and are not differentiable, which will be discussed in the next subsection.

2.3 Differentiable Logic Gates Networks

Standard Boolean operations used in Logic Gate Networks are non-differentiable, which restricts their application in learning frameworks that require continuous optimization. To address this limitation, (Petersen et al., 2022) introduced Differentiable Logic Gates Networks (DLNs) using Fuzzy Logic Gates instead of Binary Logic Gates, this allows Boolean operations to be continuous (Petersen, 2022). This approach, known as continuous relaxation extends Boolean values from the discrete set $\{0, 1\}$ to the continuous interval $[0, 1]$.

Building upon the framework presented (Petersen et al., 2022), each neuron in the network learns a probability distribution over the complete set of possible Fuzzy Logic Gates, thus allows it to choose which logic gate is the best fit for the input in the training data. Given that there are 16 possible Binary Logic Gates (as detailed in Table 2.3), we define a set of functions. The output r of each neuron is computed as a weighted sum of these gate functions:

$$r = \sum_{i=0}^{15} \mathbf{p}_i \cdot f_i(a, b), \quad \text{for } i = 0, 1, \dots, 15,$$

where the weighting coefficients \mathbf{p}_i are derived from learnable parameters (logits) $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbf{R}^{16}$ through the softmax function:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = \frac{e^{w_i}}{\sum_{j=0}^{15} e^{w_j}}, \quad \text{for } i = 0, 1, \dots, 15.$$

In the original work by (Petersen et al., 2022), the Menger or probabilistic T-norm (Menger, 1942) was implemented for these fuzzy logic gates. Under this formulation, the AND (\wedge) operation in Menger’s T-norm(T_M) can be defined as:

$$T_M(a, b) = a \wedge b = a \cdot b$$

Table 2.3: List of all Fuzzy logic gates derived from Menger T-norm.

ID	Operator	Menger T-norm	00	01	10	11
0	<i>False</i>	0	0	0	0	0
1	$a \wedge b$	ab	0	0	0	1
2	$\neg(a \Rightarrow b)$	$a - ab$	0	0	1	0
3	a	a	0	0	1	1
4	$\neg(a \Leftarrow b)$	$b - ab$	0	1	0	0
5	b	b	0	1	0	1
6	$\neg(a \Leftrightarrow b)$	$a + b - 2ab$	0	1	1	0
7	$a \vee b$	$a + b - ab$	0	1	1	1
8	$\neg(a \vee b)$	$1 - (a + b - ab)$	1	0	0	0
9	$a \Leftrightarrow b$	$1 - (a + b - 2ab)$	1	0	0	1
10	$\neg b$	$1 - b$	1	0	1	0
11	$a \Leftarrow b$	$1 - b + ab$	1	0	1	1
12	$\neg a$	$1 - a$	1	1	0	0
13	$a \Rightarrow b$	$1 - a + ab$	1	1	0	1
14	$\neg(a \wedge b)$	$1 - ab$	1	1	1	0
15	<i>True</i>	1	1	1	1	1

Source: Table from (Petersen et al., 2022) paper.

This approach enables gradient-based learning through backpropagation while maintaining interpretability. The nature of fuzzy logic gates provides a critical advantage: after training DLNs can be discretized back into standard LGNs, thereby leveraging the computational efficiency of bit-wise operations during inference without sacrificing model performance.

Chapter 3

Differentiable Logic Gate Networks based on Zadeh’s T-norm

The Boolean operations $f : \mathbf{B}^2 \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ are non-differentiable, which poses a challenge for training using gradient descent methods. To address this limitation, DLNs replace Binary Logic Gates in LGNs with Fuzzy Logic Gates, providing a continuous approximation of Boolean operations (Petersen et al., 2022).

In our current investigation, we explore the Zadeh T-norm (Zadeh, 1965) as an alternative to the Menger (Menger, 1942) approach. Using the Zadeh formulation, the conjunction operation is defined as:

$$T_Z(a, b) = a \wedge b = \min\{a, b\}, \quad \text{with } a, b \in [0, 1]$$

However, the Zadeh T-norm introduces a new consideration: the min and max operators are continuous but not differentiable. Specifically, at points where their inputs are equal (i.e., when $a = b$). To address this limitation, we learn from ReLU and implement the following piecewise function for the conjunction operation:

$$a \wedge b = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } a \leq b, \\ b & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Following (Petersen et al., 2022), each neuron in our network learns a probability distribution across all 16 possible Binary Logic Gates (Table 3.1). We define functions f_i where $i \in \{0, \dots, 15\}$, with each neuron’s output r calculated as:

$$r = \sum_{i=0}^{15} \mathbf{p}_i \cdot f_i(a, b)$$

This formulation enables the network to adaptively select the most appropriate logic gate for each neuron during training. The softmax transformation ensures that the coefficients \mathbf{p}_i form a valid probability distribution, with all values being non-negative and summing to one.

For training, we employ the Adam optimizer (Kingma & Ba, 2014), a widely-used first-order gradient-based optimization method. At initialization, pairs of randomly choose inputs are assigned to each neuron, while the neuron’s logits weights \mathbf{w}_i are sampled from a standard normal distribution. During the forward pass, each neuron’s continuous activations r are com-

Table 3.1: List of all Fuzzy logic gates derived from Zadeh T-norm.

ID	Operator	Zadeh T-norm	00	01	10	11
0	<i>False</i>	0	0	0	0	0
1	$a \wedge b$	$\min\{a, b\}$	0	0	0	1
2	$\neg(a \Rightarrow b)$	$1 - \max\{1 - a, b\}$	0	0	1	0
3	a	a	0	0	1	1
4	$\neg(a \Leftarrow b)$	$1 - \max\{a, 1 - b\}$	0	1	0	0
5	b	b	0	1	0	1
6	$\neg(a \Leftrightarrow b)$	$1 - \min\{\max\{1 - a, b\}, \max\{a, 1 - b\}\}$	0	1	1	0
7	$a \vee b$	$\max\{a, b\}$	0	1	1	1
8	$\neg(a \vee b)$	$1 - \max\{a, b\}$	1	0	0	0
9	$a \Leftrightarrow b$	$\min\{\max\{1 - a, b\}, \{a, 1 - b\}\}$	1	0	0	1
10	$\neg b$	$1 - b$	1	0	1	0
11	$a \Leftarrow b$	$\max\{a, 1 - b\}$	1	0	1	1
12	$\neg a$	$1 - a$	1	1	0	0
13	$a \Rightarrow b$	$\max\{1 - a, b\}$	1	1	0	1
14	$\neg(a \wedge b)$	$1 - \min\{a, b\}$	1	1	1	0
15	<i>True</i>	1	1	1	1	1

Source: Own elaboration.

puted through the weighted summation of the 16 Fuzzy Logic Gates $f_i(a, b)$ and the probability distribution \mathbf{p} calculated via softmax. These activations then propagate through subsequent network layers.

The backpropagation process requires careful consideration of the derivatives for each fuzzy gate type. Among the 16 fuzzy gates presented in Table 3.1, six gates ($f_{0,1,5,10,12,15}$) are trivial. The constant gates f_0 and f_{15} , which output fixed values of 0 and 1 respectively, have zero derivatives with respect to both inputs:

$$\frac{\partial f_0}{\partial a} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial b} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f_{15}}{\partial a} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f_{15}}{\partial b} = 0$$

The identity function gates f_3 and f_5 , which return either input a or b unchanged, have straightforward derivatives:

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial a} = 1, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial b} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f_5}{\partial a} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f_5}{\partial b} = 1$$

For the inversion gates f_{10} and f_{12} , which compute $1 - b$ and $1 - a$ respectively, the derivatives are:

$$\frac{\partial f_{10}}{\partial a} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f_{10}}{\partial b} = -1, \quad \frac{\partial f_{12}}{\partial a} = -1, \quad \frac{\partial f_{12}}{\partial b} = 0$$

The Zadeh fuzzy gates (Zadeh, 1965) present additional complexity due to their use of min and max functions. For instance, the AND gate ($f_1 = \min\{a, b\}$) requires special handling to address the non-differentiability when $a = b$. In our implementation, by default we use a when

inputs are equal, resulting in the following piecewise derivatives:

$$\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial a} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \leq b, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial b} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } a \leq b, \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This presents two interesting characteristics of Zadeh T -norm. Firstly, T -norm_Z gradient is always constrained to the set of three values $\{-1, 0, 1\}$. Lastly, except for constant gates f_0, f_{15} the partial derivative for $\partial f_i/\partial a$ and $\partial f_i/\partial b$ will never become zero at the same time. This results in Zadeh T -norm having very strong local gradients compared to Menger T -norm and potentially reducing gradient vanishing.

3.0.1 Discretization

Upon convergence of the training process, we perform a discretization step to transform the fuzzy logic network into a more computationally efficient binary logic network. This transformation is achieved by replacing each Fuzzy Logic Gate with its Binary Logic equivalent, specifically selecting the operator corresponding to the highest logit value at each neuron. This discretization process yields a C code file, the whole network is self-contained inside one function. Each binary logic operator is one line of code, resulting in a model with one million parameters as a C function with one million lines of code. Therefore, for models with more than 50,000 parameters we choose to compile it with a gcc compiler with optimization flag of 0, the rest is one.

The discretization process generates a C source file in which the entire network is encapsulated within a single function. Each binary logic operator corresponds to a single line of code, resulting in a one-to-one mapping between parameters and lines. Consequently, a model with one million parameters translates into a C function with approximately one million lines of code. To ensure manageable compilation times and executable sizes, we compile models with more than 50,000 parameters using the `-O0` optimization level in gcc, while smaller models are compiled with the default optimization level `-O1`.

that preserves the learned logical structure while benefiting from the computational efficiency of Boolean operations. The resulting network maintains the same topology and logical relationships established during training, but operates using discrete binary values rather than continuous approximations.

To accommodate scenarios where n output neurons $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in [0, 1]$ need to predict $k < n$ values beyond the $[0, 1]$ range, we implement an aggregation mechanism defined as:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{j=i \cdot n/k + 1}^{(i+1) \cdot n/k} a_j / \tau + \beta,$$

where τ represents a normalization temperature and β serves as an optional offset parameter, enabling flexible output scaling and adjustment.

3.1 Experiments

To empirically evaluate our models¹, we employ a diverse set of assessment across different data modalities. To this end, we curate a selection of benchmark datasets, which include both structured and unstructured data. We incorporate five widely-adopted benchmark datasets: MONK (Thrun et al., 1991), MNIST (LeCun et al., 1998), CIFAR-10 (Krizhevsky, 2012), Adult Census (Becker & Kohavi, 1996), and Breast Cancer (Zwitter & Soklic, 1988). They were selected to evaluate model performance across distinct data paradigms. The MONK, Adult Census and Breast Cancer datasets represent structured data, where each feature has a clear human-interpretable meaning, such as age, name, or year of birth. In contrast, MNIST and CIFAR-10 are collections of unstructured data in the form of images. These datasets are particularly interesting because individual pixels lack meaning when viewed in isolation - their significance emerges only through their relationship with surrounding pixels and the overall context of the image. These datasets are widely adopted benchmarks in the machine learning community, enabling direct comparison with existing research.

For our analysis, we benchmark our results against prior work by (Petersen et al., 2022) and adopt an identical hyperparameter configuration. We evaluate three key performance indicators: accuracy, inference speed, and memory efficiency. All models are implemented using PyTorch and trained on an RTX 2000 Ada GPU, while inference single thread benchmarks are conducted on an AMD Ryzen 5 3550H with Radeon Vega Mobile Gfx CPU, this choice of CPU providing insight into how the models perform in real-world scenarios with limited computing power.

On contemporary x86 processors, logical operations on boolean values are constrained by the architecture’s 64-bit arithmetic logic unit (ALU), which necessitates padding boolean values to 64 bits. In the original work by (Petersen et al., 2022) and in our paper (Wasilewski & Nguy, 2025), all boolean values were pre-padded to 64 bits. However, through our own empirical evaluations, we observed that pre-padding to just 8 bits yields superior inference times for our existing hardware. Accordingly, this thesis departs from our earlier work (Wasilewski & Nguy, 2025) by adopting an 8-bit representation for Boolean values during inference. It is worth noting that, the choice of padding width whether 8 bits or 64 bits does not impact model accuracy, as both configurations produce equivalent predictive performance.

3.1.1 MONK

The Monk (Thrun et al., 1991) datasets are a set of classification tasks for evaluating machine learning algorithms. It consists of 3 challenges of increasing difficulty to assess model generalization capabilities. Monk 1 and Monk 3 are standard disjunctive normal form while the

¹

Source code for the experiments is publicly available at <https://github.com/duong-nguy/difflogic-fuzzy-zadeh-t-norm>

Table 3.2: Accuracy results on the MONK data sets averaged over 100 runs.

Method	MONK-1	MONK-2	MONK-3
ANN	100%	100%	93.5%
DLN _M	100%	78.2%	95.4%
DLN _Z	100%	89.3%	91.7%
	# Parameters	Inf. Time	Memory
ANN	162	161.20 ± 26.50ns	648B
DLN _M	144 72 72	8.06 ± 0.17ns	72B 36B 36B
DLN _Z	144 72 72	7.77 ± 0.13ns	72B 36B 36B

Source: Own elaboration.

latter Monk 3 contains some noise. Conversely, Monk 2 is similar to parity problem. On the first dataset the results are in table 3.2, both Menger and Zadeh Differential Logic Networks perform equally well as Neural Networks, achieving perfect classification at 100%. However, on the second dataset, our method based on Zadeh’s logic shows accuracy performance substantially greater than Menger’s logic method performance (89.3% vs. 78.2%), though both fall short of Neural Networks (100%). For the third dataset, Menger-based approach (95.4%) surpasses both Neural Networks (93.5%) and our Zadeh implementation (91.7%). Interestingly, while the Zadeh’s logic network underperforms on the third dataset, it shows significant improvement over Menger’s logic network in the second challenge. Both DLNs variants demonstrate substantially faster inference times (approximately 8 ns) compared to Neural Networks (161.2 ns).

3.1.2 Adult dataset

Adult Census Income Dataset (Becker & Kohavi, 1996) is a benchmark collection from the UCI repository. It contains 48,842 samples from the 1994 US Census. Its attributes include demographic and socio-economic information, with a total of 14 different attributes from age, work class, education, and more. It is widely used for social science research and benchmarking. For this dataset, we find that the Menger-based model achieves comparable accuracy to Neural Networks (84.8% vs. 84.9%), see Table 3.3, while the Zadeh approach lags behind at 75.4%. However, both Differential Logic Networks Menger and Zadeh demonstrate significant computational advantages, with inference times of 59.47ns and 71.12ns respectively, compared to Neural Networks at 287.95ns. Additionally, DLN models require substantially less memory than Neural Networks (640B vs. 15KB), highlighting the efficiency-preserving nature of Menger and Zadeh T-norm approaches.

Although we do not report the include inference data for DLNs encoded with 64-bit padding in this thesis, it is noteworthy that the 64-bit variant of DLN_Z achieves a faster inference time compared to DLN_M under the same bit-width configuration (146.2 ns vs. 168.9 ns). This suggests that the underlying connective structure may play a role in execution efficiency, independent of the encoding size.

Table 3.3: Results for the Adult data set averaged over 100 runs.

Adult	Acc.	#Param.	Infer. Time	Memory
ANN	84.9%	3,810	$287.95 \pm 6.19\text{ns}$	15KB
DLN_M	84.8%	1,280	$59.47 \pm 2.34\text{ns}$	640B
DLN_Z	75.4%	1,280	$71.12 \pm 0.45\text{ns}$	640B

Source: Own elaboration.

3.1.3 Breast Cancer

The Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Zwitter & Soklic, 1988) dataset is commonly used in evaluating machine learning for binary classification tasks. It contains 569 samples with 40 different real-valued features computed by subject-matter experts. The dataset has two classes: malignant and benign tumors, offering a well-structured problem for testing machine learning models. In this challenging medical dataset, see Table 3.4, Neural Networks achieve the highest accuracy at 75.3%, followed by the Menger-based approach at 71.4%, while our Zadeh implementation shows the lowest performance at 68.6%. Despite the lower accuracy, both Differential Logic Networks maintain considerable speed advantages, with inference times of 38.34ns and 35.14ns respectively, compared to Neural Networks at 792.43ns. The memory requirements also favor Menger and our Zadeh-based approaches significantly, requiring only 320B versus 1.4KB for Neural Networks.

Table 3.4: Results for the Breast Cancer data set averaged over 100 runs.

Breast Cancer	Acc.	#Param.	Infer. Time	Memory
ANN	75.3%	434	$792.43 \pm 100.23\text{ns}$	1.4KB
DLN_M	71.4%	640	$38.34 \pm 0.27\text{ns}$	320B
DLN_Z	68.6%	640	$35.14 \pm 0.22\text{ns}$	320B

Source: Own elaboration.

3.1.4 MNIST dataset

For comparison to previous work with the Menger method, we evaluate our approach on MNIST. MNIST is a benchmark dataset of handwritten digits that is widely used in machine learning and computer vision research. It contains 70,000 grayscale images divided into 60,000 training images and 10,000 testing images of size 28×28 pixels. We further resize the dataset to 20×20 images to make a second dataset for testing the models with smaller size. The dataset consists of digits 0 to 9 with corresponding labels and is designed for classification tasks. It is commonly used in evaluating neural networks and is most frequently applied to convolutional neural network architectures.

Results presented in Table 3.5 show that neural networks outperform both our Zadeh-based approach and the Menger-based approach regardless of the image size. Our method achieves 94.5% for the small model and 93.3% for the normal-size model; these accuracies fall short

Table 3.5: Results for the MNIST data set averaged over 100 runs, where OPs stand for number of binary operations needed to perform computations.

MNIST	Acc.	#Param.	Memory	Infer. Time	OPs
ANN (<i>small</i>)	97.92%	118282	462KB	$3.66 \pm 0.148\mu s$	236M
DLN _M (<i>small</i>)	96.3%	48000	23KB	$1.127 \pm 0.03\mu s$	48K
DLN _Z (<i>small</i>)	94.5%	48000	23KB	$1.104 \pm 0.03\mu s$	48K
ANN	98.40%	22609930	86MB	$1009.17 \pm 9.232\mu s$	45G
DLN _M	97.6%	384000	188KB	$83.157 \pm 0.09\mu s$	384K
DLN _Z	93.3%	384000	188KB	$79.119 \pm 0.06\mu s$	384K

Source: Own elaboration.

compared to the small and normal-size Menger-based models, which achieve 96.3% and 97.6% respectively. However, our approach has much faster inference speed than the Menger-based approach: 1124.2ns vs. 1397.5ns for MNIST 20×20 and 70785.2ns vs. 73056ns for MNIST 28×28. When scaled to larger architectures, the performance gap widens, with our Zadeh approach achieving 93.3% compared to 97.6% for Menger logic and 98.40% for neural networks. Notably, despite the accuracy vs. speed trade-off, both Differential Logic Networks maintain significant advantages in terms of inference speed, parameter count, and memory footprint compared to neural networks while delivering faster inference time. The DLNs based on the Menger T-norm have more accuracy than those based on the Zadeh T-norm but they are slower.

3.1.5 CIFAR-10

CIFAR-10 (Krizhevsky, 2012) is a benchmark dataset consisting of 60,000 color images, each 32×32 pixels, categorized into 10 classes. The dataset is split into 50,000 training images and 10,000 testing images. It includes different classes of objects such as airplanes, automobiles, birds, cats, and others. Its low resolution helps researchers with limited computation to test and develop new algorithms.

We further reduced the color-channel resolution to three value thresholds for *small* and *medium* models and 31 value thresholds for *large* models following (Petersen et al., 2022). A naive conversion of pixels to binary values using 0.5 threshold will lead to loss of information. To reduce this conversion loss, authors of (Petersen et al., 2022) used three and 31 value thresholds. We have 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 thresholds for each pixel: for example $p_i = 0.3$ can be represented as $p_i = [1, 1, 0, 0]$, where i is the linearized position of a pixel. This further reduces the discretization loss from Fuzzy Logic Gates to Binary Logic Gates since the models are trained on binary input. While dropout and augmentation are common practices in computer vision to reduce overfitting, in this study we did not apply these techniques to our method.

Comparing to the Neural Networks, in the case of small models, Differentiable Logic Networks have lower accuracy but they outperform NNs with respect to other four attributes. In the case of medium models, Zadeh’s and Menger’s Logic Networks have similar accuracy but outperform NNs on the other metrics. Lastly, in the case of large models, both fuzzy logic networks

Table 3.6: Results for the CIFAR-10 data set averaged over 100 runs, where OPs stand for number of binary operations needed to perform computations, S,M,L stand for Small, Medium and Large number of parameters in the model respectively presented in the third column.

CIFAR-10	Acc.	#Param.	Memory	Infer. Time	OPs
ANN	57.08%	12.6M	48MB	$519.38 \pm 6.7\mu s$	25G
DLN _M (S)	45.75%	48K	24KB	$1.753 \pm 0.00\mu s$	48K
DLN _Z (S)	45.45%	48K	24KB	$2.002 \pm 0.003\mu s$	48K
DLN _M (M)	57.34%	512K	250KB	$167.188 \pm 0.137\mu s$	512K
DLN _Z (M)	55.55%	512K	250KB	$163.544 \pm 0.105\mu s$	512K
DLN _M (L)	60.32%	1.28M	625KB	$399.079 \pm 4.204\mu s$	1.28M
DLN _Z (L)	57.28%	1.28M	625KB	$382.808 \pm 0.161\mu s$	1.28M

Source: Own elaboration.

have slower speed than Neural Networks but they are better with respect to other attributes.

The experimental results in Table 3.6 demonstrate that Zadeh’s network accuracy increases as we increase the number of neurons per layer, similarly to the behavior observed in Menger’s networks. With the small architecture, both approaches achieve comparable accuracy (around 45.5%), but as model capacity increases, a performance gap emerges, with the Menger approach reaching 60.32% versus 57.28% for Zadeh in the large configuration. Interestingly, even our medium-sized Zadeh model (55.55%) nearly matches the performance of the neural network (57.08%) while requiring only a fraction of the parameters (512K vs. 12.6M) and maintaining significantly faster inference times (163.544ns vs. 519.38ns). This suggests that while Zadeh logic networks may not always match the accuracy of their Menger counterparts in complex visual tasks, they still offer compelling efficiency advantages over traditional neural networks.

Differentiable Logic Networks differ in accuracy and inference speed, but they are indiscernible in memory and binary complexity with respect to the size of the model. In smaller-sized models, the accuracy is about the same, but in medium and large sizes, Menger is better. However, for small and medium numbers of parameters, Zadeh’s logic networks are faster in terms of operational time than Menger’s logic networks, but with a larger number of parameters, Menger’s logic networks become faster than Zadeh’s logic networks.

Chapter 4

Analysis and Conclusions

4.1 Analysis

4.1.1 ANNs vs. DLNs

Our empirical evaluation reveals a consistent trade-off between computational efficiency and classification accuracy when comparing Deep Differentiable Logic Networks (DLNs) against conventional Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). Across all evaluated datasets, DLNs demonstrate substantially reduced inference times and memory requirements, achieving speed improvements of up to $20\times$ on smaller datasets (MONK, Adult, Breast Cancer) and $1.3\text{--}12\times$ acceleration on larger datasets (CIFAR-10, MNIST). The memory complexity reductions are particularly pronounced, with DLNs requiring orders of magnitude less memory than their ANN counterparts due to their inherently sparse computational structure.

However, these computational advantages come at the cost of classification accuracy. DLN_Z exhibits lower accuracy ranging from 1.8% (MONK-3) to 9.5% (Adult dataset) relative to standard ANNs. In contrast, DLN_M demonstrates more variable performance characteristics, occasionally outperforming ANNs by 3.2% (CIFAR-10) while underperforming by 3.9% in other cases (Breast Cancer). Notably, this accuracy gap diminishes with increased model capacity, suggesting that larger DLN architectures approach ANN-level performance while maintaining their computational efficiency advantages.

4.1.2 DLN_Z vs. DLN_M

When comparing the two DLN variants, DLN_Z consistently achieves marginally faster inference times than DLN_M , despite both methods utilizing identical parameter counts and memory allocations due to their shared underlying framework. This performance differential comes with a slight accuracy penalty, as DLN_Z generally underperforms DLN_M in classification tasks. A particularly noteworthy observation emerges from the MONK-2 dataset, where DLN_Z exhibits superior pattern recognition capabilities for specific singular patterns, suggesting potential specialization advantages in certain problem domains.

These findings indicate that DLNs, and particularly DLN_Z , represent a viable architectural choice for applications where computational efficiency takes precedence over absolute accu-

racy, making them well-suited for deployment in resource-constrained environments such as embedded systems or real-time inference scenarios including latency sensitive, energy efficient medical devices.

4.2 Conclusions

4.2.1 Characteristic of Zadeh’s logic based models

We introduced a Differentiable Logic Gate network using Zadeh’s T-norm relaxation to enable gradient-based training of discrete architectures and systematically evaluated DLNs using both Menger’s and Zadeh’s logics across diverse benchmarks. Our findings reveal that while Zadeh logic networks offer remarkable computational benefits exhibiting lower inference latency, however they tend to underperform in accuracy on more intricate tasks compared to their Menger-based counterparts. Both Zadeh and Menger logic networks also requiring less memory compared to neural networks, highlighting their computational efficiency over ANNs despite the mixed classification performance. On one hand Menger based method is robust against noise but on the other hand our Zadeh based method is much better at looking for specific singular patterns, which could be beneficial in resource-constrained medical applications where efficiency must be balanced with accuracy. This show that Zadeh’s logic based models prefer to choose the faster trivial gates such as 0, 3, 5 and 15 see table 2.1 Since our model is based on the source code for Menger Logic Network from (Petersen et al., 2022), thus it maintains the similar efficient inference speed and disk space characteristics suggesting that different logical frameworks may be better suited to specific problem structures.

4.2.2 A Different axis of optimization

Beyond architectural factors such as the number of layers or neurons per layer, our research introduces an additional axis of optimization within the Differentiable Logic Gate network framework: the choice of fuzzy logic rule. This choice proves to be a critical hyperparameter for DLNs. In datasets where distinct, isolated patterns are present, Zadeh-based DLNs demonstrate superior pattern recognition capabilities. Conversely, Menger-based DLNs exhibit greater robustness to noise, making them more suitable for tasks involving high-variance or noisy inputs. In scenarios where inference speed is prioritized over marginal drops in accuracy, DLN_Z may offer a preferable trade-off.

An additional, albeit unintended, axis of optimization emerged from our investigation into memory padding strategies. While padding to 64 bits aligns with the architecture of modern CPUs, we observed that the impact of padding can vary depending on the specific hardware. These observations open new considerations for hardware-aware optimizations of DLNs. The results contained in this thesis, were originally developed and presented as a paper at the 6th Polish Conference on Artificial Intelligence PP-RAI 2025 (Wasilewski & Nguy, 2025).

4.2.3 Future researchs

These findings underscore a fundamental trade-off between computational efficiency and predictive performance, emphasizing the importance of designing tailored regularization strategies and exploring potential hybrid architectures.

Looking forward, several directions for future research emerge. One such direction involves exploring alternative T-norm relaxations such as the Łukasiewicz T-norm. Similar to Zadeh’s formulation, the Łukasiewicz T-norm exhibits strong local gradients, however, a substantial portion of its domain remains flat, which can lead to vanishing gradient issues. This necessitates specialized training techniques to mitigate such challenges, particularly during the initial phases of optimization.

Moreover, since boolean values must be padded to 64 bits, each binary operation executed by the arithmetic logic unit (ALU) must operate over 64-bit pairs. To maximize throughput on modern GPUs and CPUs, it is advantageous for each neuron to process multiple input pairs concurrently, thereby exploiting the full width of the underlying hardware.

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